

Research Article

Teachers Motivation and Students Performance: A Correlational Study of Secondary School Teachers in District Bagh Azad Jammu and Kashmir

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 29-Mar-24 Revised: 09-May-24 Accepted: 10-May-24 Published: 11-May-24	This study was conducted to determine the relationship between motivation of teachers and students performance of Secondary school teacher in District Bagh AJ&K. The current study was descriptive in nature and survey methods were used for the collection of data. The population of the study were consisted of 304 secondary school teachers of District Bagh AJ&K. 171 teachers were selected as a sample by using simple random sampling technique. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used as a tool in this study. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation for the analysis of data. It was found that teamwork improves students learning and provide opportunities to engage problem solving skills. Moreover, students learn better when they work in groups and enjoyed when they working together. It is recommended that teacher may actively promote and incorporate teamwork in classroom settings.
Keywords:	Teacher motivation, Intrinsic motivation, Extrinsic motivation, Student performance
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Introduction

Motivation is a crucial component that supports instructors in their profession and is a heavenly boon for society. For an educational component to be developed and of high quality, a teacher has to be driven to execute his job. Motivation is a psychological notion that is crucial to academic success and has a significant impact on the quality of life in general. Motivation of teachers is crucial. Even if it's believed these days that as technology advances, work performance will rise, it's important to emphasize that instructors' constant efforts are what count most in the educational system (Setiawan, 2021).

Their ongoing motivation is essential to the educational system's ongoing improvement in the caliber of instruction. Pupils are motivated to learn for several reasons. These elements might be external or inherent. Students that are motivated learn more. Teachers' motivating support is essential in helping pupils study more. Students are naturally driven to study because they find the material or work interesting and enjoyable, which provides the lessons they acquire profound significance and implications for their life. In order to create a learning atmosphere, teachers are essential. Teachers assist students develop personal interest, participation, and ownership of their work, which contribute in motivation, by supporting their choices and interests. The effectiveness of teachers has a significant impact on both academic achievement and the quality of education. The performance of teachers is still a difficult topic in the realm of education. The teacher is the backbone of the educational system; targeted learning objectives cannot be met in the absence of improved teacher performance. By giving students the freedom to choose their own goals and objectives, teachers may also encourage responsibility and engagement in their own education (Sabah, 2020).

Positive interactions between teachers and students are more likely to impact the kids' motivation to learn. It takes time to establish trust in a relationship. It is important for teachers to spend time getting to know their pupils' interests. For teachers to provide an environment that inspires pupils to study, motivation is essential. The development of students' autonomy, relevance, relatedness, competency, instructors' interests, and teachers' self-efficacy about teaching their topic are all seen as indicators of the teachers' involvement in fostering students' motivation. Students' drive to study can come from both internal and external sources, but teachers' support of their education and provision of the ideal atmosphere can increase students' enthusiasm to learn even more (Kotherja, 2013).

The investigator conducted an instructional practicum at Government Girls High School No. 1. Throughout this time, researchers made several observations. Less incentive exists in Kotli for teachers as a vocation. This outside assistance is frequently given by teachers, who are in charge of establishing a supportive atmosphere that promotes and enhances students' learning. Teaching motivation is similar to the body's use of glucose to enable action and reaction in order to attain greater results. Instructors do not give students' performance their due attention. Not only is the student's performance declining, but so is their level of interest. Researchers wanted to work on it because of this (Muhammad, 2021).

Review of Related Literature

Motivation

Motivation is a complex concept that is hard to explain, however many authors have tried to do so by utilizing a variety of concepts and ideas. Nonetheless, it is widely accepted that motivation is what awakens human energy, which propels people to strive toward satisfying their desires and helping them reach their intended objectives. It goes without saying that when a teacher uses the incentive factor in the classroom, students' learning results and study habits improve (Petri, 2012). In addition to greater academic success, higher levels of study motivation have been linked to enhanced conceptual comprehension, school satisfaction, self-esteem, social adjustment, and school completion rates. Students' beliefs may have an effect on their motivation. For example, students who believe they have limited learning potential or are unlikely to succeed occasionally suffer with motivation. Similarly, students who think that intelligence is a fixed attribute that one either has or does not usually have lower Children may perform better in school than those who are only motivated by a love of learning if they can see learning as a launching pad to something else they value rather than merely something that will always be the same. Therefore, I argue that if certain conditions are satisfied, goals might encourage students to study more (Di Giunta, 2013).

Types of Motivation

Lifestyle, culture, and society all have a big impact on motivation. Every culture has its own sources of inspiration. Even greater influences come from lifestyle, social environment, and education (Rani, 2014).

Intrinsic motivation

The easiest way to define intrinsic motivation is as things that drive someone with the intention of receiving internal rewards. This includes any pursuits done just for enjoyment or self-gratification without any thought of receiving recognition from others. There are a ton of daily actions that are driven by intrinsic motivation. It might be exercising, picking up new skills, engaging in sports or games, or just lending a helping hand to someone crossing the street because it makes you feel good or gives you a sense of purpose (Ryan, 2017).

Benefits of Intrinsic Motivation

Numerous research from a range of fields demonstrate the many advantages of operating with intrinsic drive. These include perseverance, imagination, conceptual learning, and overall wellbeing. This chapter's goal is to examine some of the evidence that indicates these advantages of intrinsic motivation (Saari, 2012).

Persistence

Numerous studies indicate that persistence the ability to stick with something over time or in the face of a goal—and intrinsic desire are positively correlated. There is evidence of this connection in domains like physical activity (Teixeira, 2012).

Creativity

There is evidence of this connection in domains like physical activity. Hennessey claims that the majority of academics nowadays concur that value that is, the belief that these advances are

valuable to the person and/or broader social group and novelty that is, the production of a unique idea, product, or issue solution are the two fundamental elements of creativity. However, as can be seen below, several research have used different definitions and metrics for originality (Valaei, 2022).

Conceptual Learning

Numerous studies indicate that intrinsic drive supports conceptual learning. When someone learns conceptually, they have a greater comprehension of the subject matter and are able to analyze its underlying meaning and connect it to other concepts. One way to evaluate conceptual learning is to ask participants to grade statements like "I studied the text by associating the things I read with what I already knew" or to ask them what they believed to be the major point of the book. Compared to basic rote learning, which involves memorizing facts without seeking to understand their deeper significance, this type of learning is more profound (Devloo, 2015).

Well-being

Numerous pieces of evidence indicate that hedonic and eudemonic well-being are positively correlated with intrinsic motivation. Common definitions of hedonic well-being include having high levels of positive affectivity and low levels of negative affectivity, as well as subjective assessments of one's degree of overall life satisfaction and happiness with significant areas of their work (LeFebvre, 2021). It has been demonstrated that the satisfaction of the fundamental psychological demands for relatedness, competence, and autonomy is positively correlated with intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic motivation is the umbrella term for everything that functions as an external drive and is divided into two groups: rewards and punishments. As payment, one may receive an evaluation, a salary, incentives, merchandise, or cash (Zhu, 2022).

Factors of Extrinsic Motivation

The SDT was the first to shed light on the various forms of motivation, while earlier theories of motivation usually saw motivation as a single idea that varied only in amount (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Extrinsic motivation is divided into four subtypes by the SDT (Ryan & Deci, 2020):

1. External regulation: this approach views the majority of the causes of behavior as external; it has the least degree of autonomy and motivates compliance through external incentives and penalties.
2. Introduction control - seeing the source of action as somewhat external; ego involvement (e.g., self-esteem is impacted by the result); a component of seeking approval from others or oneself.
3. Identification - seeing activity as partly internal; evaluating activities or objectives consciously as having personal significance; experiencing autonomy and will.

The ultimate level of autonomy is known as integration, which also involves conscious identification and internalization of the worth of activities and objectives as well as a perception that these things are congruent with one's interests and personal values (*Ten Cate, 2011*).

Achievement Motivation

In that it seeks to accomplish an objective only for personal growth, accomplishment motivation is similar to competence motivation in several ways. It is a real-world example of accomplishment motivation where the objective is to pursue an amazing feat just for the satisfaction of reaching that height (King, 2012).

Although the term "motivation" has various definitions, a cursory examination of scientific literature and colloquial English would indicate that, at their core, they all refer to the mechanisms that propel an organism to action. It is true that the word "motivation" derives from the Latin verb mover, which meaning "to move." Therefore, the processes that result in the initiation, maintenance, intensity, and quality of behavior are referred to as motivation (Nazir, Shah, & Zamir, 2019) As a result, the phrase "achievement motivation" refers to actions that result in behavior intended to meet a certain norm or criterion. Any official or informal aim or target, established by oneself or by others, in any professional or recreational arena (e.g., school, sports, job, music, gardening, even social connections and moral behavior) can serve as the criteria, providing a framework for assessing success and failure (Seven, 2020).

Attitude Motivation

This kind of motivation stems from a desire to have a positive impact, alter the world, or assist others. It makes no difference what other people think, feel, or what energy emanates from within (Asghar, Akhter & Shah, 2020). The most important factor is that someone notices something is off and wants to assist, alter, or repair it (Wagner, 2012).

Factors that affect teacher motivation

Leadership

Teachers need leaders to keep them engaged in their profession and inspired to do excellent work. Each of their acts and behaviors has the potential to improve or worsen the workplace, which will have an effect on teachers' motivation. Leadership must be mindful of teachers' needs, dedicated to their success, and eager to make good contributions to the teacher experience that foster a sense of purpose in their work if they hope to have a positive influence on teachers' motivation (Nyamubi, 2018).

Professional Development Opportunities

Providing chances for professional growth and development is an excellent approach to assist educators in advancing in their professions. It may also have a beneficial effect on teachers' motivation by sending a message that they are important and indispensable to the success of the future. Both instructors and students can gain a great deal by offering in-person or online training, tuition reimbursement, leadership development, or scheduling time for learning throughout the workweek. Leaders can provide developmental coaching to team members to help them choose what professional development activities would best fit a teacher's goals (Oyserman, 2021).

Meaningful Work

Work that is meaningful has a purpose and makes an impression. Teachers who believe that their job has meaning and purpose are more dedicated to it because they wish to have a good influence. Many people find that working fulfills their desire to achieve their objectives and change the world. Motivation is increased when one works in a job where their work is meaningful and purposeful beyond their everyday responsibilities (Nyamubi, 2018).

Students' Academic Performance

Many research have tried to identify the variables influencing students' overall performance or accomplishment. The purpose of this review is to provide evidence for the theory that a student's performance and accomplishment in the classroom are influenced by a variety of factors, including institutional, teacher, and personal characteristics. Students' self-respect, inventiveness, and belief in their academic advancement have always had an impact on their academic achievement. Poor performance might reduce students' desire for better results, such a higher grade, and impact their future doubt about the overall outcomes of the school (Rabourn, 2018).

The policies and procedures of the institution have a significant impact on students' performance as well. The main educational sector, whether it be the public or private sector, has an impact on students' performance. A student's whole performance is intimately correlated with what occurs in the classroom (Lafarge, 2011).

Learning is the ultimate objective of education, and it is the purpose of schooling and academic success. In this context, the intricate unit known as performance consists of a number of parts. These are educational procedures supported by the school that entail changing one's current condition into a new one while maintaining integrity in an alternative unit that includes both cognitive and structural components. Performance fluctuates depending on the biological and environmental factors that define one's experiences and skill set. Academic success is influenced by a variety of elements, including self-esteem, study habits, abilities, interests, personality, motivation, and the teacher-student dynamic. Diverging performance is the term used to describe when a student's actual performance differs from their predicted performance in the classroom. A below-expected performance in academics is considered an unsatisfactory performance. Sometimes it has to do with the ways that teachers teach (Zimmerman, 2013).

It is essential to bear in mind that a student's learning methodologies are not a fixed aspect of their personality. Conversely, depending on the nature of the academic work, a student might choose between a surface or deep learning strategy. To put it another way, learning strategies are determined by the unique qualities of each student as well as the educational environment (Jackson, 2015).

Measuring students' performance

Group work

Group work gives students the opportunity to engage in process skill critical for processing information, and evaluating and solving problem as well as management skills through the use of role within groups, and assessment skills involved in assessing options to make decisions about their group's final answer. Group work improves the learning performance of students and thereby improves their achievement, skills and behaviour (Antoniou, 2013).

Creating exams

Exams provide a regulated setting for autonomous work and hence are commonly used to check students' learning. Students typically open their books more frequently when an assessment is approaching. Tests have the power to inspire greatly. Exams are a type of educational exercise. They may open students' eyes to the subject matter in new ways. Additionally, they offer comments that students may utilize to enhance their comprehension. Exams allow teachers and students to determine whether portions of the curriculum are unclear. This facilitates student growth and improvement by allowing students to ask for assistance and teachers to focus on areas that might require additional attention. Exams are a useful tool for self-evaluation in education. Exam results from students will highlight areas where you should invest more time or modify your existing strategy (Wagner, 2012).

Students' behaviour

There are two major groups, the positive and the negative academic behaviour. Positive behavior is defined as the actions that create a positive working environment and/or enabling others to work more effectively through what we say or do. Student behavior also plays a major role in academic achievement as it can affect his/her ability to learn as well as impact the learning environment for other students. Students who engage in disruptive behavior frequently or consistently may experience even more negative outcomes. These students may be excluded from the classroom (e.g., sent to the office, suspended, expelled), which means they miss important instructional and social opportunities (Podsakoff, 2014).

Research Objectives

1. To identify the motivation of teachers provided to the students at secondary school level.
2. To check the performance of students at secondary school level.
3. To examine the relationship between motivation of teachers and students performance at secondary school level.

Research Questions

1. What is the motivation of teachers provided to the students at secondary school level?
2. What are the performance of students at secondary school level?
3. What is the relationship between motivation of teachers and students performance at secondary school level?

Research Methodology

The major purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between teachers' motivation and students' performance at secondary school level in district Bagh Azad Jammu and Kashmir. This study was descriptive in nature and cross-sectional survey was applied to collect the data. 304 Government Girls Secondary School Teachers of District Bagh were the population of the study. 171 secondary school teachers of District Bagh were selected randomly from the population of the study by using of simple random sampling technique. A questionnaire was developed for secondary school teachers based on teachers' motivation and students' performance. The researcher used five point Likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree) for collecting the response from the respondents. The research instrument was validated from two experts in the

field of education. For Pilot testing questionnaire was distributed among 20 teachers of secondary schools of District Bagh who were not the part of sample. The reliability of instrument was measured through Cronbach's alpha statistical technique. The reliability of the instrument was 0.938 which was acceptable for conducting the final survey. The researcher collected the data personally from the respondents of Government Girls Secondary School Teachers through questionnaire. The collected data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and Pearson Correlation for the analysis and interpretation of data.

Results

Table 1

Mean analysis of group work

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Teamwork improves students learning ability.	171	4.58
2.	Collaboration gives students the opportunity to engage problem solving skills.	171	4.45
3.	Students learn better when they works in groups.	171	4.37
4.	Students enjoyed when they working together.	171	4.29

The table 1 that a majority of respondents strongly agreed that teamwork and collaboration enhance learning, with 86% agreeing that teamwork improves learning ability (mean rating of 4.58), 84% agreeing that collaboration enhances problem-solving skills (mean rating of 4.45), and 83% agreeing that students learn better in groups (mean rating of 4.37). While a slightly lower percentage (81%) agree that students enjoy working together (mean rating of 4.29), the overall results indicate a strong positive response to the benefits of teamwork and collaboration in learning, with mean ratings ranging from 4.29 to 4.58 out of 5.

Table 2

Mean analysis of Examinations

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	1.1.1 Papers provide a standard environment for independents work.	171	4.49
2.	Exam provides a great motivation for students.	171	4.36
3.	You provide a feedback to students for improve their understanding.	171	4.22
4.	You use exams to evaluate their own teaching.	171	4.36

The table indicates that a majority of respondents agreed on the importance of traditional assessment methods and feedback in learning, with 85% agreeing that papers provide a standard environment for independent work (mean rating of 4.49), 83% agreeing that exams provide great motivation for students (mean rating of 4.36), and 83% also agreeing that exams help teachers evaluate their own teaching (mean rating of 4.36). Additionally, 80% agree that feedback is provided to students to improve their understanding (mean rating of 4.22). Overall, the results indicate a strong positive response to the role of traditional assessment methods and feedback in learning, with mean ratings ranging from 4.22 to 4.49 out of 5.

Table 3

Mean analysis of Behavior

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Positive students' behaviour creates a better working environment.	171	4.66
2.	Students' disruptive behaviour may lead negative outcomes.	171	4.30
3.	Behaviour plays a major role in students' performance.	171	4.41
4.	Your students learn effectively when they work in comfortable environment.	171	4.34

table 3 depicts that a vast majority of respondents strongly agreed that students' behavior plays a crucial role in creating a productive learning environment, with 90% agreeing that positive behavior creates a better working environment (mean rating of 4.66), 83% agreeing that disruptive behavior leads to negative outcomes (mean rating of 4.30), and 85% agreeing that behavior significantly impacts students' performance (mean rating of 4.41). Additionally, 84% agree that students learn effectively in a comfortable environment (mean rating of 4.34). Overall, the results emphasize the importance of a positive and comfortable learning environment, with mean ratings ranging from 4.30 to 4.66 out of 5.

Table 4

Mean analysis of teachers motivation

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Your leadership motivate teacher to do great work.	171	4.51
2.	Your management behaviour impact teacher working environment.	171	4.25
3.	Your leader provides guidance without pressure.	171	4.22
4.	Teacher is quite competent in doing his/her job.	171	4.25

table 4 shows that a majority of respondents agreed that leadership and management play a significant role in shaping the work environment and motivation of teachers, with 86% agreeing

that leadership motivates teachers to do great work (mean rating of 4.51), 81% agreeing that management behavior impacts the working environment (mean rating of 4.25), and 80% agreeing that leadership provides guidance without pressure (mean rating of 4.22). Additionally, 81% agree that teachers are competent in their jobs (mean rating of 4.25). Overall, the results suggest that effective leadership and management are crucial for creating a positive work environment and motivating teachers, with mean ratings ranging from 4.22 to 4.51 out of 5.

Table 5

Mean analysis of Professional development opportunity

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Professional opportunity helps in your career.	171	4.46
2.	Job satisfaction positively impact in your future success.	171	4.35
3.	Your principal offer improvement coaching for teachers.	171	4.11
4.	You share your teaching experiences with colleagues face to face.	171	4.16

Table 5 describes that a majority of respondents agreed that professional opportunities and job satisfaction are essential for career success, with 85% agreeing that professional opportunities help in career advancement (mean rating of 4.46) and 83% agreeing that job satisfaction positively impacts future success (mean rating of 4.35). Additionally, 79% agree that their principal offers improvement coaching for teachers (mean rating of 4.11), and 80% share their teaching experiences with colleagues face-to-face (mean rating of 4.16). Overall, the results highlight the importance of professional growth, job satisfaction, and collaborative sharing of experiences in teaching, with mean ratings ranging from 4.11 to 4.46 out of 5.

Table 6

Mean analysis of meaningful work

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Relevant work helps you accomplish teaching goals.	171	4.52
2.	You pay most attention on students' success.	171	3.37
3.	Your purposeful work increase opportunity for improving teaching task.	171	4.31
4.	Your school teachers working condition is good.	171	4.32

table 6 illustrates that a majority of respondents agreed that relevant work and purposeful efforts are crucial for achieving teaching goals and improving teaching tasks, with 87% agreeing that relevant work helps accomplish teaching goals (mean rating of 4.52) and 83% agreeing that purposeful work increases opportunities for improving teaching tasks (mean rating of 4.31).

Additionally, 82% agree that their school's working conditions are good (mean rating of 4.32). However, only 64% agree that they pay most attention to students' success (mean rating of 3.37), indicating a relatively lower level of agreement on this statement. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of focused work and good working conditions in teaching, with mean ratings ranging from 3.37 to 4.52 out of 5.

Table 4. 7

Correlation of teacher motivation and student's performance

No	R	Sig-value
1 Teacher motivation		
	.865	.000
2 Student performance		

Table 7 shows the results correlation analysis, between teacher motivation and student performance. The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.865, indicating a strong positive relationship between the two variables. The significance value (Sig-value) is 0.000, which is less than the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the correlation is statistically significant. This means that as teacher motivation increases, student performance also tends to increase, and vice versa. The strength of the correlation (0.865) suggests that the relationship is substantial, and the significance value (0.000) indicates that the correlation is unlikely to be due to chance.

Discussion

This statement highlights the importance of teamwork and collaboration in improving student learning outcomes. Research has consistently shown that teamwork and collaborative learning activities promote deeper understanding, improved retention, and enhanced problem-solving skills among students (Johnson & Johnson, 2017). When students work in groups, they have the opportunity to share ideas, learn from one another, and develop essential skills such as communication, critical thinking, and leadership (Wagner, 2010).

Moreover, teamwork and collaboration provide students with a sense of belonging and enjoyment, leading to increased motivation and engagement in the learning process (Hastie et al., 2017). This is particularly important in today's diverse and interconnected world, where teamwork and collaboration are essential skills for success in both personal and professional settings (Dillenbourg, 2017).

Research highlights the significance of student behavior in creating a conducive learning environment and its impact on academic performance. Research has consistently shown that positive student behavior, such as respect, attentiveness, and engagement, creates a better working environment that fosters academic achievement (Wang, 2019). On the other hand, disruptive behavior, such as bullying, absenteeism, and misconduct, can lead to negative outcomes, including decreased academic performance, social problems, and emotional distress (Henderson, 2017).

Moreover, behavior plays a crucial role in student performance, as it can either enhance or hinder the learning process. Students who exhibit positive behavior tend to be more motivated, focused,

and engaged in their learning, leading to better academic outcomes (Martin, 2018). In contrast, students who display disruptive behavior may struggle academically, experience decreased self-esteem, and develop behavioral problems (McLeod, 2017).

Furthermore, a comfortable learning environment is essential for effective learning. When students feel safe, supported, and comfortable, they are more likely to engage in the learning process, take risks, and develop a growth mindset (Dweck, 2017). Teachers can create a comfortable environment by promoting positive relationships, using inclusive language, and incorporating diverse perspectives (Gay, 2018).

The study's findings, which reveal a statistically significant and strong positive relationship between teacher motivation and student performance ($r = 0.865$), are consistent with recent research highlighting the critical role of teacher motivation in enhancing student outcomes (Kraft & Papay, 2014; Rivera-McCutchen, 2018). The positive correlation suggests that as teacher motivation increases, student performance also tends to improve, and vice versa, underscoring the importance of prioritizing teacher motivation to support student success (Wagner, 2018).

Research has shown that motivated teachers are more likely to create engaging and supportive learning environments, which can lead to increased student motivation and engagement (Martin, 2018). Moreover, teacher motivation is linked to teacher self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and commitment, all of which are essential for effective teaching and student learning (Bandura, 2012; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012).

The findings of this study have implications for educational leaders and policymakers, emphasizing the need to prioritize teacher motivation and well-being to improve student outcomes (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2017). Strategies such as providing opportunities for professional growth, recognition, and autonomy can help boost teacher motivation and, in turn, enhance student performance (Guskey, 2014; Hattie & Timperley, 2007).

Conclusions

1. Teamwork improves students learning and collaboration gives students the opportunity to engage problem solving skills leadership. Moreover, students learn better when they work in groups and students enjoyed when they working together.
1. Papers provide a standard environment for independent work and exam provide a great motivation for students. Moreover, you provide a feedback to students for improve their learning and you use exams to evaluate their own teaching.
2. Positive students' behaviour creates a better working environment and students' disruptive behaviour may lead negative outcomes. Moreover, behaviour plays a major role in student's performance and your students learn effectively when they work in comfortable environment.
3. Your leadership motivate teachers to do great work and your management behaviour impact teaching working environment. Moreover, your leader provides guidance without any pressure and teacher is quite competent in doing his/her job.
4. Professional opportunity helps in your career and job satisfaction positively impact in your future success. Moreover, your principal offer improvement coaching for teachers and you share your teaching experiences with colleagues face to face.
5. Relevant work helps you accomplish teaching goals and you pay most attention on students' success. Moreover, your purposeful work increase opportunity for improving teaching skills and your school teachers working condition is good.

6. It is concluded that there is found statistically significant and strong positive relationship between teacher motivation and student performance, with a correlation coefficient of 0.865. This indicates that as teacher motivation increases, student performance also tends to increase, and vice versa. The findings suggest that teacher motivation plays a crucial role in enhancing student performance, and efforts to boost teacher motivation are likely to have a positive impact on student outcomes.

Recommendations

1. Educators and school administrators are recommended to actively promote and incorporate teamwork in educational settings. This can be achieved through structured group activities, collaborative projects, and fostering an environment that encourages students to work together. By doing so, students will not only enhance their learning experience but also develop essential problem-solving and leadership skills, creating a more enjoyable and effective learning environment.
2. It is recommended that educators continue to utilize a combination of papers and exams in the classroom. This approach offers a standard setting for independent study, motivates students effectively, and facilitates valuable feedback for their improvement. Furthermore, the use of exams as a tool for evaluating teaching methods is encouraged to enhance the overall learning experience.
3. Based on the study's conclusion, it is recommended that the leadership style be maintained, as it effectively motivates teachers and positively influences the teaching working environment. The guidance provided without pressure has proven beneficial, highlighting the importance of continuing this supportive leadership approach for sustained teacher competence and success.
4. Teachers are encouraged to continue their dedicated and purposeful work, focusing on students' success. This not only enhances teaching skills but also contributes to a positive working environment for all school teachers.

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